

DESIGNING AN INTEGRATED THERMOCHEMICAL BIOREFINERY WITH A NOVEL HYDROGEN RECYCLING CONCEPT

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Hydrogen is a key component in a hydrotreatment-based biorefinery. This work presents an alternative biorefinery concept integrating renewable hydrogen production by water electrolysis and an electrochemical compressor for hydrogen recovery. The proposed system is simulated in AspenPlusTM and consists of five major subsystems: pyrolysis, hydrotreatment, gas conditioning, electrochemical compression and water electrolysis. The overall system is energetically evaluated and key parameters affecting the overall efficiency are identified. After upgrading, the produced oil fraction contains 34% less oxygen compared to the bio-oil feedstock and 47% of the energy content of the initial biomass feedstock. Also, 32% of hydrogen is consumed during hydrotreating and 19% during gas cleaning, resulting in 49% being available for H₂ recirculation using the electrochemical compressor. This results in 38% of the hydrogen needs (in energy value terms) being derived from recirculated H₂, and as a consequence, less power is required for producing fresh H₂ by water electrolysis.

Keywords: biorefinery, hydrogen, upgrading, recycling, modelling

1 INTRODUCTION

In an analogous manner with a petrochemical refinery, the scope of the biorefinery concept is to efficiently integrate different conversion technologies to produce chemicals, fuels or electricity from biomass. In a hydrotreatment-based biorefinery, the scope is to convert the initial solid, biomass feedstock into a valuable, liquid product that could either be used directly as fuel or as feed for co-processing in a petrochemical refinery [1]. The latter demands a single, mild upgrading step to reduce the moisture and oxygen content of the bio-feed instead of two steps for the former [2]. Before the hydrotreatment (HDT) system is the pyrolysis step, which reaction conditions determine the quantity and quality of the produced bio-oil. Fast pyrolysis conditions, such as short vapor residence time and temperatures around 500 °C are mainly suitable for the production of bio-oil as the main product. Other products include biochar and gases that can be used internally for heat production [3].

Hydrogen is the key component in the hydrotreatment process and its purpose is the removal of the contained oxygen heteroatoms. For the production of hydrogen various technologies can be employed, depending on fossil (natural gas, coal etc.) or renewable sources (biomass, water etc.). The state-of-the-art hydrogen production process is methane steam reforming. Despite of the lower cost of fossil-based technologies, the environmental impact is a parameter that should also be taken into consideration [4]. It is assumed that for every kg of produced hydrogen, 7.33 kg CO₂ are emitted in contrast to the carbon-free, water electrolysis process [5]. Despite of today's higher cost of renewables, usage of environmentally friendly methods and technologies is a prerequisite for building a green future. This higher cost of renewables renders more important the need to exhaustively optimize processes in terms of efficiency and energetic requirements.

Bio-oil hydroprocessing requires high excess of hydrogen, having as a consequence, large fraction of the initial H₂ remaining unexploited. In order to maximize the efficiency of the process, it is useful to recycle the residual H₂ and thus avoid the cost and power associated to producing fresh H₂ by electrolysis.

An alternative technology to recover hydrogen from a gaseous mixture is electrochemical hydrogen compression. An electrochemical compressor (EHC) has similar construction to a proton exchange membrane (PEM) fuel cell and has the ability to recover H₂ from a gaseous mixture and pressurize it [6]. The operating principle is simple: a gaseous mixture containing H₂ is fed to the anode, where hydrogen is selectively oxidized to protons and electrons. Electrons travel through an external circuit and protons through the membrane. Then they are recombined at the cathode forming molecular hydrogen, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Electrochemical hydrogen compression principle of operation

Compression occurs using a back-pressure valve [7]. The main difference between an EHC and a PEM fuel cell, is that during electrochemical compression, the voltage difference (and in consequence the input power) is the driving force of the occurring electrochemical operations. The combination of recovery and compression in a single step, is the major advantage against the state-of-the-art pressure swing adsorption that requires multiple columns operating under consecutive cyclic steps [8]. The EHC can be operated in three different modes: i) only for H₂ recovery, ii) only for H₂ compression and iii) for H₂ recovery and compression using an EHC solely or in combination with a mechanical compressor.

Before entering the EHC, the feed gas requires conditioning due to contained impurities in the HDT off-gases. These include hydrogen sulphide and carbon monoxide, which should be restricted to avoid poisoning

and deterioration of system's performance. Therefore, a ZnO bed to reduce H₂S and a CO methanation reactor were introduced before the EHC system.

The scope of this work is to study the efficient integration of a hydrotreatment-based biorefinery with a renewable hydrogen production and an alternative recycling concept. The proposed biorefinery system is shown in Figure 2 and is simulated using the AspenPlus™ simulation software. The complete biorefinery chain is energetically assessed and focus is given on the efficient hydrogen utilization. The target is to identify processes and operating parameters that decrease the overall efficiency and propose ways of improvement.

Figure 2: Integrated Biorefinery Concept

2 SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The proposed biorefinery scheme consists of five major subsystems: pyrolysis, hydrotreating, gas conditioning, hydrogen recirculation and hydrogen production. Each section is described in brief below.

The lignocellulosic biomass feed is firstly dried and grinded before entering the pyrolyser. Since bio-oil is the main product of interest, fast pyrolysis is the preferred pyrolysis mode. After separating the biochar using cyclones and filters and the permanent gases using quench coolers, the remaining bio-oil is stored for further processing.

The produced pyrolysis oil is fed into the mild-hydrotreating reactor for upgrading/stabilization using H₂, in order to reduce the moisture and oxygen content. The HDT products consist of three phases: an organic, an aqueous and a gaseous phase. The organic fraction is further processed into the conventional petrochemical refinery to produce hybrid fuels or chemicals. The gaseous stream is mainly composed of unreacted hydrogen, carbonaceous gases (such as CO, CO₂, CH₄ etc.) and H₂S, due to the usage of a sulphided HDT catalyst. The recovery of the residual hydrogen using an electrochemical compressor is investigated in this work.

Prior to entering the EHC, the feed gas requires conditioning to avoid poisonous or degradation effects on the electrochemical system. The inlet pressure of the gaseous stream is restricted to <10 bar and therefore a turbine was placed to decompress the gas and extract the useful work thereof. Apart from the inlet pressure, the contained H₂S and CO have to be previously removed [9,10]. Based on past experimental works it is suggested to keep H₂S levels in the order of ppbs (for modelling purposes, it is proposed <10 ppbs) [11] and CO levels

under 10 ppm [12]. This is performed by integrating two gas polishing steps: i) H₂S deep removal using a ZnO bed and ii) CO methanation reactor (CO MET). In addition, adequate hydration of the membrane is crucial for the conductivity of the EHC membrane. Therefore, a humidifier is placed before the electrochemical compressor to saturate the gaseous feed and fulfil the water demands of the system.

After the conditioning steps, H₂ is recovered in the EHC at a higher pressure and compressed at the final pressure with a mechanical compressor. Finally, it is mixed with fresh, renewable hydrogen produced by water electrolysis and reused at the hydrotreating reactor.

3 METHODOLOGY AND SIMULATION DESCRIPTION

The studied biorefinery concept is assumed to be a midscale unit that processes 270 ktn/h of biomass feedstock, operating approximately 7500 hours per year. The biomass feedstock is considered of woody origin with properties and ultimate analysis depicted in Table 1. The ultimate analysis of the initial biomass feedstock as well as of the subsequent bio-products serves as the basis for each mass balance calculation and for the calculation of the corresponding heating value.

Table 1: Biomass Feedstock Properties [13]

Variable	
Biomass Type	Wood
Moisture	7.8
Ash	0.2
<i>Ultimate analysis (daf)</i>	
Carbon	49.6
Oxygen	44.1
Hydrogen	6.1
Nitrogen	0.1
Sulphur	0.06

For the calculation of the higher and lower heating value of the biomass feedstocks and bio-products, following empirical equations were used [14]:

$$HHV_{daf} = -1.3675 + 0.3137C + 0.7009H + 0.0318(100 - C - H - Ash)$$

$$LHV_{daf} = HHV_{daf} - [9H + H_2O]\Delta H_{fg}$$

where C , H , O are the dry ash free weight basis of carbon, hydrogen and oxygen, H_2O and Ash the moisture and ash contents and ΔH_{fg} the latent heat of water vaporization (= 2,257 kJ/kg).

The energy content of a gaseous mixture depends on the heating value of the gases comprising the mixture:

$$LHV_{gas} = \sum m_i LHV_i$$

where m_i and LHV_i are the mass flow and heating value of each gaseous species.

The assumptions as well as specifications of each process section are shown in Table 2.

For the calculation of the energy efficiency of each subsystem, the lower heating value of the product of interest is compared to the inlet streams and the required

power/heat. Figure 3 illustrates the followed methodology and the inlet/outlet streams of each system.

Table 2: Process specifications and assumptions

Variable	Value
<i>Pyrolysis</i>	
Biomass Feed, kg/s	10
Pyrolysis Temperature, K	773
Cooling Temperature, K	303
<i>Hydrotreating</i>	
HDT Temperature, K	523
HDT Pressure, bar	100
<i>Gas Cleaning</i>	
Turbine Efficiency, %	75
Decompression Pressure, bar	10
ZnO bed Temperature, K	473
CO methanation Temperature, K	473
<i>Electrochemical Compression</i>	
H ₂ Recycling Ratio, %	80
EHC inlet pressure, bar	10
Current Density, A/cm ²	0.5
EHC Temperature, K	343
EHC Pressure ratio	2
Mechanical Compressor Efficiency, %	75

Figure 3: Energy efficiency calculation methodology

3.1 Pyrolysis

The scope of the pyrolysis model is to accurately predict the mass balances and product yields (bio-oil, char and gases), their corresponding composition as well as the energetic value thereof. The developed model is based on semi-empirical correlations extracted by a variety of experimental data [15].

There are several available methodologies in literature for the rough estimation of the heat of pyrolysis [16]. Each methodology depends on different assumptions for the evolution of the pyrolysis process. In this work, the adopted empirical correlation is based on the heat required for vaporization and the heat for water evaporation [17]:

$$Q_{pyro} = 991. + 3392 \frac{H_2O}{1 - (H_2O + Ash)}$$

where H_2O and Ash refer to the moisture and ash contents of the biomass feedstock.

3.2 Bio-oil Hydrotreating

The modelling methodology of the hydrotreatment

system is based on the ultimate analysis of the bio-oil feed and the product phases (upgraded oil, aqueous, gases). The ultimate-analysis approach simulates accurately the atomic and total mass balances as well as the hydrogen consumption of the process, which is the main focus of this work. The hydrotreating reactor is represented by an AspenPlusTM RYield reactor and the mass balances of the process are evaluated in Fortran subroutines [18]. The sulphided catalyst has not been taken into consideration for the mass balance calculations and the formed H₂S was added afterwards, in quantities dictated by past experimental works [19].

For the estimation of the hydrotreating reaction heat, at first the enthalpy of formation of the involved biomass species is calculated. The calculation of the standard heat of formation is based on the heat of combustion, based on the correlations described above. It is also assumed that combustion results in the complete oxidation of all involved elements. The heat of formation is then based on the involved stoichiometric coefficients and heat of formation of the formed gaseous species [20].

3.3 Gas cleaning

Simulation of the ZnO bed and the CO methanation reactor has been conducted using equilibrium-based approaches in the AspenPlusTM simulation software.

3.3.1 Hydrogen sulphide adsorption

Hydrogen sulphide adsorption is a deep sulphur removal process that allows to contain the adsorbed sulphur in the form of ZnS. Due to the contained CO and CO₂ in the HDT off-gases, additional reactions could occur, yielding the also poisonous carbonyl sulphide:

Table 3: Reactions occurring during H₂S adsorption

Reactions	
$ZnO_{(s)} + H_2S \rightarrow ZnS_{(s)} + H_2O$	(R1)
$H_2S + CO \rightarrow COS + H_2$	(R2)
$H_2S + CO_2 \rightarrow COS + H_2O$	(R3)

Adsorption is usually conducted at temperatures below 300 °C and, as illustrated by the stoichiometry of the occurring reactions, reaction pressure does not affect equilibrium. However, water is formed during the reaction and if water is present in the inlet feed, the reaction could be shifted towards the reactants hindering thereby, the efficient removal of H₂S [21].

3.3.2 CO methanation

In an analogous manner with H₂S adsorption, additional reactions could occur during CO methanation. Apart from carbon monoxide methanation (R4), the CO₂ methanation and gas shift reactions could occur (R5, R6), as indicated in Table 4. This results in higher H₂ consumption and, thus, less hydrogen being available for recirculation [12].

Table 4: Reactions occurring during CO methanation

Reactions	
$CO + 3H_2 \rightarrow CH_4 + H_2O$	(R4)
$CO_2 + 4H_2 \rightarrow CH_4 + 2H_2O$	(R5)
$CO_2 + H_2 \rightarrow CO + H_2O$	(R6)

3.4 Electrochemical Hydrogen Compression

The basic principles of electrochemical hydrogen compression bare similarities to the known principles of PEM fuel cell operations. The amount of hydrogen transferred from anode to cathode is proportional to the applied current as dictated by Faraday's law. The EHC operation is driven by the Nernst voltage, which indicates the minimum voltage that has to be supplied for a certain compression ratio. However, higher voltage is required because additional losses occur within the system. These include the Ohmic losses, due to the resistance of the membrane, and activation losses, due to hydrogen evolution and oxidation reaction kinetics at the anode and cathode, respectively.

The developed EHC model takes into consideration the aforementioned overvoltages for the calculation of the overall power requirements and cell voltage. The steady-state, zero-dimensional model is developed in AspenPlus™ using basic unit operation blocks to represent the main electrochemical operations, whereas voltage, current density and power requirements are calculated and implemented into Fortran subroutines. Several operating parameters including the hydrogen back diffusion, cooling requirements and water management can be estimated. Detailed description of the technology and the developed model can be found elsewhere [22].

3.5 Water electrolysis

Comprehensive modelling of the electrolysis section is not within the scope of this work. For the calculation of the overall electrolysis power requirements, the basic aspects of the process have been taken into consideration. It is assumed that highly pure hydrogen (>99.9%) is produced by the water splitting process. Based on literature data of PEM electrolysis processes, the specific power consumption is set to 54.5 kWh/kg and the outlet pressure is 14 bar [23]. The overall power demands also include the power for compressing the produced hydrogen to the HDT pressure.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 6 shows the process flowsheet of the studied biorefinery concept and Table 6 shows the results of the numbered streams. Approximately 68 % of the initial biomass feed is converted to bio-oil and the rest to biochar and gases. The produced pyrolysis oil contains high contents of oxygen and moisture, which is reduced in the subsequent step of hydroprocessing. The product yields of the pyrolysis and hydrotreatment sections are shown graphically in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Mass balances of pyrolysis and hydrotreatment sections

As it can be seen from Table 6, the formed organic phase contains 33% less oxygen and 11.7 % moisture compared to 33.9% of the initial feed. Also, approximately 32% of the initial hydrogen feed is consumed during HDT resulting in a large fraction of the initial feed remaining unexploited. Apart from H₂, the gaseous phase contains CH₄, CO, CO₂ and C₂H₆ as well as H₂S.

After reducing the pressure of the gaseous phase with a gas turbine down to 10 bar, it is introduced into the ZnO bed. It can be seen that H₂S is deeply removed within tolerated ranges by the electrochemical compressor (under 10 ppb), while the formed carbonyl sulphide is in trace quantities below levels of posing threat to the EHC. In the methanation section, apart from the contained CO, CO₂ is also entirely converted to CH₄. This results however, in higher hydrogen consumption (around 19% of the inlet H₂) leading to lower available H₂ for recycling.

Figure 5 illustrates the hydrogen consumption and the available amount for recycling using the electrochemical compressor. After hydrotreating and gas cleaning, only 49 % of the initial hydrogen is available for recovery. After recovering 80% of the remaining H₂ in the EHC at a higher pressure (this case 20 bar), it is compressed with a mechanical compressor to the final HDT pressure (100 bar).

Figure 5: H₂ consumption and available amount for recycling

Table 5 shows the energy efficiency of each process, based on the methodology described in Section 3. The low efficiency of the pyrolysis process is attributed to the endothermic nature of the process. Pyrolysis is a heat-driven process that requires energy for the scission of the comprising biomass macromolecules. A known solution to increase the efficiency of pyrolysis is to combust the two by-products (char and gases) for heat that can be used internally. The hydrotreating process, on the other hand, is an exothermic reaction. The upgraded oil product compared to the other formed products is more energetically valuable, resulting in higher process efficiency.

Table 5: The energy efficiency of the individual processes.

Process	%
Pyrolysis	49.3
Hydrotreating	66.3
Gas conditioning	89.4
Electrochemical Compression	31.5
Water Electrolysis	61.0
Total	41.3

The losses occurring in the gas conditioning section are mainly attributed to the two occurring reactions but

Figure 6: Process flowsheet of the integrated biorefinery scheme

Table 6: Stream Results (* indicates trace quantities)

Nr.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Stream Name	Biomass	Char	Gases	Bio-Oil	H ₂ Feed	Upgraded Oil	Aqueous Phase	Gases	Gases after ZnO	Conditioned Gases	Anode Outlet	Recirculated H ₂
m (kg/s)	10	1.81	1.47	6.89	0.17	3.36	3.18	0.67	0.60	0.60	0.33	0.07
T (K)	298	773	303	303	523	523	523	523	473	473	343	343
P (bar)	1	1	1	1	100	100	100	100	10	10	10	100
% vol. fraction:					99.9;			71.3; 2.9;	73.5; 5.1;	57.9; *; *;	29.2; 0; 0;	99.7; 0; 0; 0;
H ₂ ; CO ₂ ; CO;			3.7; 47.5;		0; 0; 0;			2.9; 17.1;	0.6; 17.1; 1;	25.7; 1.1;	65.0; 2.7;	0; 0; 0.3
CH ₄ ; C ₂ H ₆ ; H ₂ S;			38.5; 9.5;		0; 0; 0;			1; 5; 0; 0	*; *; 2.7	0; 0; 15.3	0; 0; 3.1	
COS; H ₂ O			0.8; 0; 0; 0		0.1							
wt.% daf basis	49.6; 6.1;	79.3; 2.5;		56.8; 7.4;		74.3; 7.7;	18.0; 14.1;					
C; H; O; N; S;	44.1; 0.1;	14.3; 3.1;		35.7; 0.02;		17.9; 0.01;	67.7; 0.1;					
H ₂ O	0.06; 10.1	0.8; 0.1		0.01; 33.9		0.01; 11.9	0.02; 80.9					

especially to the nature of the H₂S adsorption process. A considerable mass fraction of the inlet gases (H₂S) is adsorbed and retained as zinc sulphide, yielding thus lower mass of gaseous products. On the other hand, the efficiency of the electrochemical compression system, is 31% due to the anode outlet gases that have a considerable energetic value.

In Table 7 the energetic value of the initial biomass feedstock is compared to the products and side-streams of the biorefinery concept. It also indicates that recycling of the residual amount results in 38.2% of the total hydrogen needs (in energy value terms) being derived from recirculated H₂. As a consequence, less power is required compared to producing fresh H₂ by water electrolysis.

Table 7: Energy contents of streams related to initial biomass feedstock (% LHV_i/LHV_{feed})

Stream	%
Biomass	100
Biochar	26.9
Bio-oil	56.5
Perm. Gases	5.4
H ₂ Feed	12.8
Upgraded Oil	46.7
Aqueous Phase	4.3
Gaseous Phase	16.9
EHC Anode Outlet	10.9
Recirculated H ₂	4.9

The upgraded oil fraction contains almost 47% of the initial feedstock, which illustrates the need to valorize any side stream, in order to maximize the overall efficiency of the process. For example, biochar and gases contain over 30 % of the initial biomass feedstock and could be used internally within the pyrolysis process. The other material stream that could be valorized is the anode outlet gaseous stream. It contains almost 11 % of the initial biomass feedstock, due to the high methane content, and could also be used for heat/power generation or additional hydrogen production.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This work investigated the design of a hydrotreatment-based biorefinery integrating an electrochemical compressor for hydrogen recirculation. AspenPlus™ simulations have shown that the upgraded oil product contains 46.7 % of the energy of the biomass feedstock with total efficiency 41.3 %. Hydrogen was consumed throughout the hydrotreatment and gas cleaning systems resulting in 49 % being available for recovery using the electrochemical compressor. Recycling of 80 % of this remaining hydrogen, resulted in 4.9% of the total 12.8% hydrogen needs being derived from recycling, avoiding thus the additional costs of electrolysis. Future work includes the techno-economic analysis of the biorefinery scheme and the comparison with existing state-of-the-art technologies.

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